

Indica-japonica discriminate parameters of specific fragments were then computed following the method of Morishima and Gadrinab (1987) with a slight modification (Zhuang et al 1995).

Meanwhile, the 52 varieties were assayed with all the indica-japonica differentiation probes except RG869 and RG684. The discriminate parameters of specific fragments were calculated as $(D_i - D_j) = 1$ for indica fragments and $(D_i - D_j) = -1$ for japonica fragments. Average discriminate values of specific varieties were calculated and plotted (Fig. 1). Two sets of probes generated similar results, but the degree of indica-japonica differentiation was enlarged by the differentiation probes, as expected.

A similar study was conducted for 20 accessions of *O. rufipogon*. Based on data from the 11 differentiation probes and 113 fragments of 40 DNA probes, average discriminate values of the specific accessions were calculated and plotted (Fig. 2). All followed a general trend. However, the differentiation probes revealed a distinguishable differentiation for indicas and japonicas within *O. rufipogon* while the randomly selected probes did not.

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1. Average indica-japonica discriminate values of 52 rice varieties.

^aBased on data of 11 subspecies differentiation probes.
^bBased on data of 184 fragments of 65 polymorphic probes.

2. Average indica-japonica discriminate values of 20 accessions of *O. rufipogon*.

^aBased on data of 113 fragments of 40 polymorphic probes.
^bBased on data of 11 subspecies differentiation probes.

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Overwintering ability of Dongxiang wild rice in Wuhan District, China

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Dongxiang wild rice is found in Dongxiang County, Jiangxi Province, in the rice belt of central China. The climate is typically continental with extreme minimum temperatures below -10°C . Dongxiang wild rice belongs to *Oryza rufipogon*, which is widely distributed from 18° to 28° $14'$ northern latitude in China.

Wild rice species have been studied to identify useful properties for rice breeding programs, but reports are few on their abilities to overwinter. Therefore, we studied the overwintering ability of Dongxiang wild rice.

In 1993, 14 accessions of *O. rufipogon* were collected from Guangdong, Guangxi,

Sprouts from the overwintered stubble of Dongxiang wild rice.

Hunan, and Jiangxi provinces and planted in ricefields in Wuhan District. Normal management practices were followed. Plants were left in the field to overwinter naturally. Many seedlings were growing in the stubble in the spring of 1994. Seedlings were pulled up to ascertain from where they came. Most had germinated from seeds shed during the previous year, but some had sprouted from underground stems.

Dongxiang wild rice was retested in 1994. This time, the panicles were bagged after heading and the aboveground plant parts were cut off to prevent seed-germinated seedlings. Only stubble remained over winter. In the spring of 1995, when the seedlings were about 15 cm, stubble was removed to inspect growth (see figure). The underground stems were yellowish green and viable, and the roots were white and able to support new plant growth. The underground stem had three nodes, with 1-3 seedlings or buds regenerating from each (see figure).

Sprouted seedlings were transplanted into pots and into the field. Those germinated from seeds served as a control. The plants in pots were subjected to a 10-h short-day treatment. Heading occurred in late July. The average seed-setting rate was 54%, which was the same as for the control. The spikelets turned black at maturity and were prone to shattering. The plants in the field grew vigorously and developed more

than 30 tillers per hill. Heading occurred in late September.

Wuhan is 2.3 ° higher in latitude than is Dongxiang County. The extreme minimum winter temperatures were -8.0 °C in 1993 and -3.5 °C in 1994. The underground stems and roots of Dongxiang wild rice have strong cold tolerance, enabling the plants to survive the winter and to grow again in early spring.

Dongxiang wild rice is an ideal source of cold tolerance. It could potentially be used to develop a new type of rice that can overwinter in rice-growing areas with climates similar to that of central China. ■

Genetic basis of variation in weedy rice collected from Republic of Korea

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Variations in morphophysiological characters—such as grain shape (length/width ratio), glume hair length, 100-grain weight, resistance to KClO₃ phenol reaction, seed dormancy, and seed shattering—and allelic variation at 14 isozyme loci were tested for 141 strains of weedy rice selected randomly from more

than 1,000 strains collected from farmers' fields in the Republic of Korea. We investigated variations in 37 restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) and 13 randomly amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) markers from 24 strains in addition to seed fertility of F₁s between weedy and cultivated rices.

Based on grain shape, Korean weedy rices were classified into long- and short-grained types. The long-grained type came only from the southern regions of the peninsula, while the short-grained type was distributed throughout the peninsula. The F₁s of long-grained weedy rice and indica testers had 48% seed fertility and those with japonica testers, 27%. Those of short-grained weedy rice and indica testers had 37% seed fertility and those with japonica testers, 69%.

By principal component analysis based on morphophysiological characters and isozyme variations, the weedy rice strains were divided into two distinct groups (see figure). All of the long-grained strains were grouped into the same cluster as indica cultivars IR36 and Peh-kuh; all of the short-grained types were clustered with japonica cultivars Taichung 65 and Nakdongbyeon. In RFLP analysis, a high level of polymorphism was found between long-grained and short-grained type, while lower polymorphism was found within each grain type. Variations in the short-grained type were narrow but those in the long-grained type were broad. The long- and short-grained types were also distinctly classified by RAPD markers.

Scatter diagram of 141 strains of Korean weedy rices by the first vectors of principal component analysis based on morphophysiological (Im) and isozyme (Ii) variations.